

Comparison of Properties of Conventional & 3D-printed Titanium & Their Mechano-Regulative Potential

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INTRODUCTION: There is a growing trend of use of 3D-printed implants made of titanium alloys. It is also known that the microstructure and topology of porous layers are different from similar conventional materials made by sintering or powder spraying technology. In this way local fluid permeability and respectively nutrients transport are also varied. Here we are analysing elastic properties and respective mechano-regulative index (MRIX) variations for different titanium specimens during representative loading scenarios.

METHODS: Strips of titanium of 10 x 40 mm were made from a rolled metal sheet (conventional) and by 3D-printing with electron beam melting. Mechanical properties were measured with DMA 242E “Artemis” (Netzsch Gerätebau GmbH, DE) in 0.1-20 Hz and 1-30 μm flexion amplitude range. Surface topology digitizing was performed from μCT scans to create a 3D micromodel, Fig. 1. Modelling of deformation and associated generated fluid flow (COMSOL Multiphysics 5.3a) was made with HP Apollo 6000 XL230a supercluster (CSC - IT Center for Science, FI). Mechano-regulative index (MRIX) as by [1] was compared for different titanium specimens during typical loading scenarios.

Fig. 1: Micro-model of surface layer of 3D printed titanium (100x100x20 μm).

RESULTS: There are identified differences in mechanical properties of titanium made by different methods. 3D-printed specimen having higher bending modulus than conventional one

(~61 GPa vs. ~47 GPa at 1 Hz), meaning 3D printed titanium will deform less at the same applied load.

Dynamic deformation of conventional titanium specimen will respectively generate higher adjacent fluid velocities, Fig. 2, than for surface of 3D printed specimen. This results in a higher fluid velocity share contribution for more "smooth" surface to MRIX than for "rough" (3D-printed).

Fig. 2. Fluid velocity magnitude ($\mu\text{m/s}$) at micro level domain (Fig. 1) at 1 Hz for deformation on x-axis for 3D printed titanium.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS: At micro level, for 3D printed titanium there is expected a wide dispersion of generated fluid velocities, and cells attached to this surface will also have more dispersion of the biomechanical cues these cells will be sensing. There could be also noticeable differences in mechanical properties of conventional and 3D printed Ti, needed an assessment for correct design of implants.

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REFERENCES: [1] J. Biomech. 30 (1997), 539-548.